

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING METHODS IN THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS ON THE BASIS OF AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH

¹Radjapova Zukhra Tirkashevna, ²Abdurafova is Umida Isamiddin's daughter

¹TDPU pffd(phd) vbdocent in the charter name

²TDPU "Regular name" "Methodology of preschool education"

2nd stage graduate student of the department

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Abstract. *Pedagogical study and teaching methodology, creation of a teaching methodology complex of each of the special subjects allocated to the technology of training specialists, attention to the integration of the content of these subjects, study guides used by students and teachers of these subjects, the development of didactic material collections and their system, the selection of effective forms is a rather complex and long-term arduous task that requires sufficient attention.*

Keywords. *didactic material, interdisciplinary communication, methodological science, training, critical assessment, modern knowledge, assessment, mental attitude, process, opinion.*

Integrative premises are based on interdisciplinary connections. Dispatch of knowledge of an interdisciplinary nature helps to integrate education and harmonize human relations with nature by producing a modern scientific picture of the world. Students' integrative journey of knowledge, ability to critically evaluate the studied phenomena has an important impact.

Our goal is to prepare students for professional activity by combining methodical sciences with interdisciplinarity. We reveal the harmony of the methodology of speech development, the theory of introduction to nature and teaching mathematics. Acquaintance with nature - mental, aesthetic relations - is related to the content of knowledge acquired by the child. moves . Knowledge of the laws of nature, which are sufficiently accessible to children's perception, takes place in observing the attitude towards nature.

Today, as one of the highest problems of educational support, we can cite the low level of communication skills among students for higher education and the problems that can make them independent. If students cannot connect subjects in harmony, their knowledge will be fragmented and they may face a number of problems in their professional activities. For example, ensuring the unity of the activity processes, teaching the members of the pedagogical team about their personal characteristics, working with the help of others in creating pedagogical efficiency with the students and the administration's parents, and hokozas. This may take the form of a loss of self-development over the course of years of the material educator's work, but the educator loses a lot of time. It is necessary to get a deeper education with students. There is a basis for the quality of education and improvement of teachers' work on themselves and the implementation of pedagogy in their activities. For this, we use the most effective trainings in the classroom.

GENERALIZED TRAINING promise means to find properties, signs, symptoms and combine them from this common general content. In generalization, things are combined.

Participants can also be admitted to the training for assignments. It is better to collect the tasks by dividing the points into groups of two or three, rather than in groups. In order to determine the winning group, the score of the person who managed to say the first answer should be recorded on the scoreboard. According to the result of accumulated points, the winning group emerged. In this case, after explaining the tasks, the teacher quickly reads the words in the task one after the other in order. At the beginning, the group should be able to find the common signs of the words read aloud. The important thing is to be the first to say the answer. If they say the correct answer, the whole group should be given points.

There may be some noise during training. Because the answers to the tasks given are of average complexity, and as a rule, you do not ask for a turn or permission to tell the story. You just have to be the first to say the right answer. The purpose of the training is to observe the ability to correctly pronounce the task given by the majority of people. Based on the help of the teacher, it is necessary to control the implementation of the words in the given task, explaining the general usage according to the convenience.

This training is tailored to the skill production audience. The training consists of fifty tasks related to various subjects and fields. Based on the content of his subject, the teacher who has to use the training should adjust the problems in it according to the subject and the class, age and level of his students. you will be given a series of words derived from generalization. The words have something in common. The words collectively represent one. Your task is to have time to say the resulting general.

Example. Hasan-Husan, Fatima-Zuhra. If we generalize, who are understood?

Answer. Gemini is understood.

Set of assignments:

1. Choleric, sanguine, phlegmatic, melancholic. If it is generalized, what kind of experience is created?
2. Lemon, tangerine, orange, banana, pineapple, kiwi. In general, what fruits are understood?
3. Water, fire, earth, air.
4. Kubroviya, Nakhishbandiya, Yassaviya, Motrudiya. If we generalize, what faith paths are understood?
5. Egypt, Sudan, Senegal, Somalia, Ghana. If we generalize, where are the management companies understood?
6. Lieutenant, captain, colonel, general, marshal. What ranks or ranks are formed if we generalize.
7. Call, cubit, mil, farsah, yard, foot. If we generalize, what units of measurement are understood?
8. March, April, May. What months are understood when generalized?
9. Bear, lion, hyena, tiger, wolf? What kind of animals are understood when generalized.
10. English, Russian, French, German, Spanish, Arabic? What languages are understood when generalized.
11. Horticulture, bee-keeping, cocoon-keeping, juvo-keeping, milling, cattle-breeding, poultry-breeding. What is meant by generalization?
12. Humo, Simurkh, Qaqnus. In general, what kind of birds are understood?

13. Trapezium , rhombus, cone, triangle, pyramid. What forms are understood when generalized?

14. European, Mongoloid, Negroid . What is meant by generalization?

15. Eagle , falcon , hawk, kyrgyz. If we generalize, what kind of birds are understood?

Training is a very popular and widespread form of installation in a wide range of fields of activity. Professional creation, from many parts, at the same time, training technology is one of the educational forms that help to understand the need to support a person's mood, attitude to a certain type of activity, self-education and self-development. is one

Training comes from the English language, " **train** ", " **training** " has many meanings, i.e.: to teach, to train, to practice (training). The word "training" has many meanings and the appearance of work with the individual as a factor of production in the form of science. physical , it consists of personal production in various spheres of social activity, in which the communication skills of an individual or a collective group are developed through a system of special tools.

Including:

- preparation of specialists for effective implementation of their future activities;
- development of mutual cooperation in educational institutions;
- determination of communication competence in all interpersonal relationships in the social environment;

Summary

It can be concluded that training is a type of training that is conducted through various games and exercises to create the skills and abilities necessary for the formation of a person that exists or can be created. Development of intelligence to apply innovations on the basis of pre-school education, to ensure that he manifests himself as a perfect person. These were sociologically analyzed by GNEshchanova in a series of articles. The main goal of trainings for future educators is to prepare them for professional activities, and this process is clearly reflected in the activities of the training.

Training activities:

1. Correcting the person's own knowledge.
skills , skills and habits manifested in professional activity .
3. Necessary qualities manifested in effective communication, observation of social norms, correction of inadequacies.
4. Developing self-awareness, knowledge and the ability to maintain correct relationships with others.
5. In general, such as ensuring and adjusting adaptation of personal social relations to activity, pelogological and social relations in it.

It is impossible to form a complex of personal and professional abilities of a person without improving the communicative competence of the person, without changing his social relations, without revising his general attitude towards the social world and himself.

From the above definitions of training, it can be said that training is a purposefully organized process, an active physical activity aimed at creating in the process of learning and effectively producing the future development of a person. Such a training concept takes field practice and provides personal development. According to the purpose of the training held in the observation of the integrative productivity of future educators, it is of different description.

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